

Milestone 4

Producing protocols for phenotyping, resilience to stresses, vegetative propagation, 'omics' on fruit and leaves, and non-food uses

Due date of milestone: 31/12/2024

Actual achievement date: 06/12/2024

Work package concerned: WP3

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'Milestones' are control points in the action that help to chart progress. They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverables, allowing the next phase of the work to begin or be needed at intermediary points (go-no-go point).

A milestone, contrary to a deliverable, will not be submitted on the EU participant portal but some part of it will be used on the EU portal.

The core of this report (all sections except annexes) should be short (~1 page and a half). Details can be added as annexes.

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Abstract

Half page/one-page maximum

This Milestone is a crucial step to ensure the reproducible phenotypic characterization of wild core-collections of *Malus*, *Pyrus* and *Prunus* fruit trees along the WP3 of the FRUITDIV project. The phenotypic traits targeted are tree phenology, resistance to stress and vigor (T3.2), ability to be vegetatively propagated (T3.3), as well as ornamental and ecophysiological traits (T3.5). T3.4 specifically targets the prediction of fruit quality traits with omics, for which we produced protocols for metabolomics and phenomics on leaves and fruits. Since the start of the project, we proceeded to protocol collection among the partner involved in WP3. Some have been provided via connections with other ongoing or completed scientific projects, while others have been created *ex nihilo* and may need further testing, validation and/or standardization. This Milestone provides the protocols in a standardized and short format with metadata on the version and a contact person. Our aim is to update and enrich this database in the 4 following years and to publish the protocols on a dedicated platform to ensure access and reproducibility of our work.

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1 Background

Objectives of WP3 are to: i) Contribute to the *ex-situ* conservation of CWRs and establish a long-term experimental design for an efficient phenotyping allowing to disentangle genetic effects and GxE interactions in CWRs, ii) Characterise the phenotypic variability in CWRs populations and existing core-collections, iii) Produce phenotypic data along with metadata formatted for WP4 that will be used for genetic-phenotype modeling in WP5.

The project preparation and the kick-off meeting have allowed to establish rules of functioning, to identify contact persons and to list target orchards necessary for the progress of WP3.

Previous projects have contributed to set-up of experimental designs and produce protocols of interest for FRUITDIV, such as STONE (European “People” program, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/246795>, 2011-2014), FREECLIMB (Prima project <https://primafreeclimb.com/project/> 2018-23) FRUITRESCUE (BNP Paribas, 2023-2026) and INNOBREED (Horizon, <https://innobreed.eu/>, 2022-2026).

The objective of this Milestone is to ensure that common protocols are properly collected, formatted and shared in the FRUITDIV project to disseminate robust methods within the consortium and beyond.

2 Work done and current status

The list of common traits to measure has been drafted on December 7th 2023 via an online meeting with partners involved in WP3, and confirmed during the Kickoff Meeting (in person, Bordeaux, January 29th to February 1st 2024). Some protocols were already existing at the start of the project, and some have been produced in this first year. Follow-up meetings have been organized by Task with all partners involved (T3.2 : 4/7/24 and 1/9/24, T3.3 : 8/7/24 and 1/10/24, T3.4: 5/4/24, 23/9/24) to discuss about protocols and their use in the field. To implement the protocols in orchards, on-site calibration sessions among the technicians involved in scoring were conducted on several dates throughout the season. We provide here a list of protocols with their status (approved, ongoing, planned). Most protocols are dedicated to phenotyping methods in the orchard (mainly T3.2), while others are intended to be applied to controlled conditions (mainly in T3.3) or in the laboratory (T3.4). As the network of core-collection orchards is not complete yet, only a few partners have applied the presented protocols on their collections. Each approved protocol can be found in Annexes. This Milestone document is planned to be updated annually with revised protocols, with the new version's date clearly indicated in the document. Older protocols will be archived. New protocols will be discussed during monthly meetings (which are organized for each genus separately). Additionally, we decided to format the protocols in the io format for a better dissemination in 2025 (<https://www.protocols.io>).

Table 1. Summary of available protocols and their status.

Task	Protocol Name	Target species	Resp. person	Status
T3.2	Phenological traits	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Morgane ROTH	Approved
T3.2	Biotic stress	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Morgane ROTH	Approved
T3.2	Abiotic stress	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Pavlina DROGOUDI	Approved
T3.2	Phenological traits	<i>Malus</i> and <i>Pyrus</i> sp.	Monika HOFER	Approved
T3.2	Scab and fire blight inoculation	<i>Malus</i> sp.	Julie FERREIRA de CARVALHO	Ongoing
T3.2	Biotic stress in orchards	<i>Malus</i> sp.	Julie FERREIRA de CARVALHO	Ongoing
T3.3	Cutting and rooting ability	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Ana PINA	Approved
T3.3	Grafting ability	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Ana PINA	Approved
T3.4	Leaf and fruit sampling for omics	<i>Malus</i>	Nicola BUSATTO	Approved
T3.4	Leaf and fruit sampling for omics	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Pierre Petriacq	Approved
T3.4	Metabolomics	All FRUITDIV species	Nicola BUSATTO	Approved
T3.4	NIRs measurements	All FRUITDIV species	Morgane ROTH	Ongoing
T3.5	Ecophysiological traits	All FRUITDIV species	Angelo NOLE	Approved

3 Deviations or delays

3.1 Description/ reason (if applicable)

Due to a delayed start of Task 3.5, no protocols have been gathered so far for that Task. Several protocols need further improvement such as for the scoring of vegetative bud break in wild apricot, which will be addressed by an on-field intercalibration in early 2025 at INRAE.

3.2 Impact on other tasks (if applicable)

Delays in providing protocols for T3.5 affects the collection of phenotypic data.

3.3 Corrective actions to be taken to come back to schedule (if applicable)

An online meeting with Task leaders of T3.5 is scheduled in January to propose protocols to apply in 2025. These decisions will be shared to the consortium during the Annual Meeting.

4 Annexes

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T_{3.2}	SOURCES : INRAE GAFL Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 18/10/24 Date of update : Contact person : Morgane ROTH morgane.roth@inrae.fr
	BIOTIC STRESS IN WILD APRICOT	

Objectives

This protocol contains scoring guidelines for biotic stress response in *P. armeniaca* in naturally infected orchards managed under low phytosanitary inputs.

Main principle

The assessment of the damages caused by all pests and diseases is based on the visual estimation of symptom incidence (percentage of damaged leaves/branches). Different rating scales are used to best capture the phenotypic expression each pest or disease. For some pests and diseases, the damages are scored with two variables describing the incidence (percentage of damaged leaves) and the severity (average percentage of symptoms per affected leaf) of symptoms. The product between intensity and severity gives an integrative trait that will be considered in following analyses. Each rating class has an equivalent in percentage in terms of the range of organs affected (for example, a '2' for powdery mildew indicates that between 1% and 10% of leaves show symptoms.). Therefore, for the following analyses, these damage scores will be transformed into percentage values (corresponding to the centre of each class) in order to work with quantitative data which can be comparable between each pests or diseases monitored.

1. Blossom blight caused by *Monilinia* spp.

The assessment is performed around 100 days after blooming date, in such a way that all symptoms are expressed and well visible before the development of leaves. All shoots infected by *Monilinia* spp. must be pruned after the observation. The incidence of blossom blight is estimated by assessing the percentage of flowering branches dried out by *Monilinia* spp. in relation to the total number of flowering branches on the tree. This implies that branches without flowers are not accounted for.

2. Shot hole caused on leaves by *Wilsonomyces carpophilus* and *Pseudomonas syringae*

This class of symptoms is broad and may correspond to a response to a variety of pathogens. Indeed, the pathogen involved in shot hole may differ between trees, genotypes and years and its identification via molecular methods using fresh leaf samples remains a challenge.

Score	Frequency = % of leaves presenting symptoms	Intensity = mean leaf area presenting symptoms
0	0 % (no symptoms)	0 % (no symptoms)
1	≤ 10 %	≤ 10 %
2	>10 et ≤ 30 %	>10 et ≤ 30 %
3	>30 et ≤ 60 %	>30 et ≤ 60 %
4	>60 et ≤ 80 %	>60 et ≤ 80 %
5	>80 %	>80 %

3. Rust on leaves caused by *Tranzschelia* spp.

Score	Frequency = % of leaves presenting symptoms	Intensity = mean leaf area presenting symptoms	Leaf Fall = % of canopy lost due to rust
0	0 % (no symptoms)	0 % (no symptoms)	0 % (no leaf fall caused by rust)
1	≤ 10%	≤ 10%	≤ 10%
2	>10% et ≤ 30 %	>10% et ≤ 30 %	>10% et ≤ 30 %
3	>30% et ≤ 60 %	>30% et ≤ 60 %	>30% et ≤ 60 %
4	>60% et ≤ 80 %	>60% et ≤ 80 %	>60% et ≤ 80 %
5	>80%	>80%	>80%

4. Bacterial canker on wood

Scoring takes place between May and June, after the scoring for blossom blight, and long enough after the vascular system reactivation to let the symptoms develop. For each tree, symptom intensity is estimated by evaluating the percentage of branches dried by canker with the following scale: 0, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%.

5. Symptoms of scab, mildew, coryneum and corky spots on fruits

When fruit load is high enough, sample 50 fruits as close as possible from the maturity date and score the proportion of fruits with symptoms. In the case of scab, score disease intensity from 0 to 3. If fruit load is too low, a simpler protocol can be adopted by assessing directly the scores on trees in the orchards (no fruit sampling).

Score	% of fruits with visible symptoms
0	0
1	1 à 2%
2	3 à 10%
3	11 à 25%
4	26 à 50%
5	>50%

6. Leaf curl caused by *Taphrina deformans*

Proceed to the counting of the leaf curl bunches, followed by their removal (prophylaxis).

7. Aphids

Proceed to scoring as soon as aphids are visible and repeat the scoring every two to four weeks until aphid leave the tree. If possible, identify the aphid species. Please mind that aphid presence are scored, not symptoms *per se*.

Score	Colonisation de la plante
0	No aphids observed
1	Only few aphids or larvae without visible symptoms on leaves
2	1 à 10% of branches infected with living colonies
3	11 à 25% of branches infected with living colonies
4	25 à 50% of branches infected with living colonies
5	> 50% of branches infected with living colonies

Contributors: Jean-Marc Audergon, Laurent Brun, Alain Blanc, Marie Serrie, Mathilde Le Pans, Amandine Fleury, Sabrina Viret, Véronique Signoret.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.2	SOURCES : INRAE GAFL Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 18/10/24 Date of update : Contact person : Morgane ROTH morgane.roth@inrae.fr
	PHENOLOGY IN WILD APRICOT	

Objectives

This protocol contains scoring guidelines for bolting date, blooming date, flower traits and maturity date in *P. armeniaca*. All phenological descriptors should be expressed as Day of the Year (DOY). The day of year (DOY) is the sequential day number starting with day 1 on January 1st.

Bolting date

Scoring must be realized 1 time per week to report the date corresponding to the stage 3.

Flower density

Should be estimated when the tree reached **Date Flo_50** to **Date Flo_100** (re-assessment between the two stages allowed). The scale goes from 0 (no flowers) to 5 (high density).

Blooming date

Scoring must be realized 2 to 3 times per week to cover D to G99 stages for each tree.

Date Flo_10 : start of flowering, with 10% of flowers at F stage (fully open)

Date Flo_50 : 50% of flowers at F stage (fully open)

Date Flo_100 : full bloom, 100% of flowers at F stage (fully open)

Flower necrosis

Estimated at **Date Flo_50**, amount of necrotic flower buds (falling down when sweeping branches). The origin is either physiological or bacterial.

Score	Flower necrosis per tree
0	No necrosis
1	Few necrosis < 20% , not significantly impacting production
2	Production is lightly impacted, 20-60% of flowers are necrotic
3	Production is strongly impacted, 70% to 100% of flowers are necrotic

Flower abnormality

Estimated at **Date Flo_50 and before Date Flo_100**. Abnormal flowers fall early from the tree and have no pistil, or present a necrotic and/or short pistil. The tree should be shaken vigorously (ex. foot kick) to see if flowers fall down. Flowers on the ground should be manually opened to inspect the pistil (at least 5 flowers).

Score	Flower abnormality per tree
0	No flower falling down when shaking the tree
1	Few abnormal flowers on the ground, no strong impact on production
2	Significant number of abnormal flowers on the ground, strong impact on production

Frozen flowers

Percentage of flowers with frozen petals (they become brown) during the period of flowering traits scoring.

Maturity date

The date corresponds to the commercial maturity. Plan several scorings every week from maturity onset in the orchard (should be around May).

Contributors: Jean-Marc Audergon, Laurent Brun, Alain Blanc, Marie Serrie, Mathilde Le Pans, Amandine Fleury, Sabrina Viret, Véronique Signoret.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.2	SOURCES : ELGO-DIMITRA Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 18/10/2024 Date of update : Contact person : Pavlina DROGOUDI pdrogoudi@elgo.gr
	ABIOTIC STRESS FROST RESISTANCE IN WILD APRICOT	

Objectives

This protocol describes the methodology for assessing frost resistance. The critical temperatures affecting the bud and wood associated damage will be evaluated in wild apricot, at different development stages.

Frost hardiness will be estimated by exposing shoots to different frost temperatures between -4°C and -12°C and by assessing tissue damage by the electrolyte leakage method and visual damage.

Materials required

- A cooled incubation chamber (EB—D, Snijders, Germany, or other)
- Conductivity meter
- Autoclave

Step by step methodology

1. SHOOT COLLECTION

One-year-old shoots will be collected during the winter-spring months. Samples will be wrapped in wet paper, sealed in plastic bags, and kept at 5°C during transportation from the field to the laboratory.

2. FREEZING PROCEDURE

One-year old shoots will be collected and immediately transferred to the lab for experimentation. Shoots will be washed with deionized water and placed in a cooled incubation chamber (EB—D, Snijders, Germany) for exposure to low temperatures. The treatment initiation will be similar to the field temperature when sampling. The cooling rate will be 2°C h . Samples will be kept at final temperature for 1 h and then removed from the cooled incubation chamber. Five shoots per genotype will be tested.

3. ELECTROLYTE LEAKAGE

Twenty milliliters of deionized water will be added to each tube, shaken for 1 h (250 rpm) at 23°C , and kept at room temperature for 24 h before the first electrical conductivity (EC1) measurement will be carried out. Samples will then be autoclaved at 120°C for 20 min to allow maximum leakage of ions, cooled at room temperature for 2 h, then EC (EC2) will be measured again. Relative electrolyte leakage (REL) will be calculated using the formula: $\text{REL} = (\text{EC1}/\text{EC2}) \times 100$.

4. MORTALITY PERCENTAGE

Visual inspection on mortality will be made three days after the freezing treatment. Mortality will be calculated by dividing the number of dead stem samples by the total number of samples.

Cold hardiness will be expressed as LT50 (lethal temperature at which 50% of the total ion leakage occurs; or, in the case of visual mortality, the lethal temperature at which 50% of the tissues are dead) by fitting response curves with the following logistic sigmoid function (Fiorino and Mancuso, 2000).

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.2	SOURCES : ELGO-DIMITRA
	SCREENING FOR DROUGHT RESISTANCE WITH THERMAL CAMERA IN WILD APRICOT	Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 18/10/2024 Date of update : Contact person : George PANTELIDIS gpantelidisi@elgo.gr

Objectives

This protocol describes the methodology for screening drought resistance with a thermal camera in wild apricot. Thermal images will be collected using a thermographic camera from which plant evotranspiration will be estimated via image analysis. The objective is to identify genotypic differences in transpiration and stomatal conductance (estimated by measuring leaf temperature with thermal imaging) under conditions of decreasing water availability. Since we do not know the threshold for the onset of drought stress condition and because this threshold might be different among genotypes, we should monitor transpiration along the progressive decline of soil available water before the wilting point (i.e. 60-70%, 40-50%, 20-30% of available water).

Materials required

Thermal camera: Model FLIR E85 (resolution 384 × 288 pixel).

Thermal images will be processed with an appropriate tool (FLIR software) in order to estimate **CWSI** or **Ig** indices.

Step by step methodology

Period of collecting thermal images

The best period for thermal image acquisition will be actively determined by the monitoring of SVWC (Soil Volume Water Content). For the first round of thermal image collection we need all the trees full irrigated (control) and the second round of thermal image collection (stressed) is when the soil available water is before the wilting point (i.e. 40-50% of available water).

Set up of Thermal Camera

1. Construct the control with two pieces of cardboard and a small rewritable surface to include 'plant number'. The centre of the cross should be in the centre of the canopy
2. Images should be acquired between 11:00 AM and 15:00 PM. The estimated time is 1 minute per tree. Therefore, we can phenotype around 240 trees per day.
3. Before image acquisition calibrate your camera emissivity at 0.95.
4. The camera saves both thermal image and a simple photo (check camera settings).
5. Set autofocus to speed up the focusing process. Use always the same autofocus position (e.g. the centre of cross). The FLIR camera has also integrated the MSX function that allow to have the contour of the objects in the images). A good approach is to set the right focus based on the references.
6. Apply water with a spray bottle in one of the cardboards until is completely wet.

7. The most important factor is the camera distance from the tree so, use the same distance from the tree (1,5 meter), also maintaining the cross with wet and dry references at the same distance from the camera (1 meter). Maintain the wet references fully-wet. The angle we take the picture is also important.
8. Try to avoid objects or spaces with too much differences of temperature because they can affect the measures.

Image analysis

1. Thermal images will be processed with FLIR software in order to estimate **CWSI** or **Ig** indices.
2. **CWSI (crop water stress index)** is calculated by the formula: $(T_{\text{canopy}} - T_{\text{ref.wet}}) / (T_{\text{ref.dry}} - T_{\text{ref.wet}})$
3. **Ig (index of relative stomatal conductance)** is calculated by the formula: $(T_{\text{ref.dry}} - T_{\text{canopy}}) / (T_{\text{canopy}} - T_{\text{ref.wet}})$
4. **T reference wet** and **T reference dry** are simply calculated by the average temperatures in an area of given size (e.g. 1 cm x 1 cm) chosen with the mouse-pad after opening the image with the FLIR software
5. **T canopy** is calculated by the average of 3 areas in the tree canopy (we will test various approach, e.g. the use of shaded leaves in the middle-lower portion of the crown, well-exposed leaves on the higher portion of the crown)

Both indices will be used to compare the genotypes.

References:

Costa et al. (2013) Thermography to explore plant–environment interactions. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 64(13): 3937–3949.

Coupel-Ledru et al. (2019) Multi-scale high-throughput phenotyping of apple architectural and functional traits in orchard reveals genotypic variability under contrasted watering regimes. *Horticulture Research* 6:52.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T_{3.2}	SOURCES : JKI Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 29/10/24 Date of update : Contact person : Monika HÖFER monika.hoefer@julius-kuehn.de
	PHENOLOGY IN POME FRUIT	

Objectives

This protocol contains scoring guidelines for bud burst, flowering stages, flower intensity and maturity date in *Malus* spp. (*Malus sylvestris* and *Malus orientalis*) and *Pyrus pyraster*.

The description for the phenology stages are based on the BBCH scale for Pome fruit (Meier et al., 1994). All phenological descriptors should be expressed as Day of the Year (DOY). The day of year (DOY) is the sequential day number starting with day 1 on January 1st.

Bud burst (BBCH 53)

Bud burst: green leaf tips enclosing flowers visible. Scoring must be realized 2 times per week to report the exact date for each tree.

Flowering (BBCH 61; BBCH 65; BBCH 69)

Scoring must be realized at least 2 times per week to cover the stages for each tree.

BBCH 61 Beginning of flowering: about 10% of flowers open

BBCH 65 Full flowering: at least 50% of flowers open, first petals falling

BBCH 69 End of flowering: all petals fallen

Flowering intensity

Should be estimated when the tree reached **BBCH 65**. The scale goes from 0 (no flowers) to 9 (extremely high density).

Maturity of fruit (BBCH 87)

The date of fruit ripening for picking corresponds to the commercial maturity. Plan several scorings every week from maturity onset in the orchard (August - October).

BBCH 87 Fruit ripe for picking

Leaf fall (BBCH 95; BBCH 97)

Scoring must be realized at least 2 times per week to cover the stages for each tree.

BBCH 95 50% of leaves discoloured

BBCH 97 All leaves fallen

Reference

Meier, U., et al. (1994) *Phänologische Entwicklungsstadien des Kernobstes (Malus domestica Borkh. und Pyrus communis L.), des Steinobstes (Prunus-Arten), der Johannisbeere (Ribes-Arten) und der Erdbeere (Fragaria x ananassa Duch.)*. Nachrichtenblatt des Deutschen Pflanzenschutzdienstes 46, 141-153.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.3	SOURCES : CITA
	PHENOTYPING FOR TRAITS LINKED TO VEGETATIVE PROPAGATION AND CULTIVATION IN WILD APRICOT	Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 01/11/2024 Date of update : Contact person : Ana PINA SOBRINO apina@cita-aragon.es

Objectives

This protocol describes the methodology for establishing effective methods for vegetative propagation and cultivation, ensuring the survival and proper development of wild apricot cultivars at different stages of development in wild apricot (*P. armeniaca*). In addition, the study aims to evaluate key agronomic traits associated with graft compatibility and rooting ability. To achieve this, two vegetative propagation techniques are performed: cuttings and grafting.

Materials required for cutting and grafting

Wood cuttings without leaves should be pruned at the beginning of January and stored at 4 °C until use. Cuttings (from each branch, up to 4 cuttings) are prepared for cutting and rooting experiments, each one being up to 20 cm long and up to 5 mm thick. Each shoot should have at least 3 buds and the branches should be healthy, with no visible damage. Grafting occurs during spring of the same year. The rootstock should be one-year-old plants with a diameter of 1 cm, and 10-15 grafts per combination are grafted with the chip-budding technique.

Step by step methodology for cutting and rooting abilities

- 1. Fungicide Treatment:** Treat the cuttings with PREVICUR (1.5 ml in 1 liter of water). Spray the solution onto the cuttings and allow the fungicide to dry completely during 1- 3 hours. Afterwards, cut the cuttings 1 cm below the bud. Some cuttings will be left intact (without incision), while others will be incised by peeling the stem around the bud with a scalpel (with incision at 1-3 cm long at the base of the cutting).

- 2.**
- 3. Hormone Preparation:** Prepare the hormone solution using indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) at concentrations of 2000 ppm (2000 mg/L) and 1000 ppm (1000 mg/L). Keep the solution refrigerated at 4°C until use. Note: To prepare 500 mL, 1g hormone is dissolved in 250 ml alcohol 96% and 250 ml dd water.
- 4. Hormone Application:** Once the cuttings are ready, dip them into the hormone solution for 8–10 seconds, ensuring the buds are properly oriented.
- 5. Wrapping and storage:** Wrap the cuttings in plastic bags to prevent dehydration and block light exposure. Place the wrapped cuttings in an in a growth chamber at approximately 22°C for 10 days to maintain a constant temperature.

6. **Planting:** After 10 days, plant the cuttings in cutting trays containing a mixture of 3 parts peat and 1 part perlite. Keep the trays in a shaded house until evaluation.
7. **FIRST EVALUATION:** Visual inspection for sprouting will be made 3 months after cutting and samples will be classified into five categories as depicted here:

8. **SECOND EVALUATION:** the cuttings will be taking out from the trays 4 months after cutting for rooting evaluation. Cuttings will be scored based on the number of roots formed:

- Only callus formation
- 1–10 roots
- 10–20 roots
- More than 20 roots

Step by step methodology for chip grafting

A video is available upon request (apina@cita-aragon.es)

1. **Cut the Rootstock:** Make a small horizontal cut to create a tongue (this tongue will help secure the scion in place) and then make a cut.
2. **Cut the scion:** Make a cut and make a corresponding tongue cut on the scion to match the tongue on the rootstock.
3. **Join the Scion to the Rootstock:**

- **Align the Cambium Layers:** carefully fit the scion onto the rootstock, aligning the cambium layers (the thin green layer just under the bark) of both pieces as closely as possible. This alignment is crucial for successful grafting.
- **Secure the Graft:** Wrap the graft union tightly with parafilm to hold the scion in place and to prevent moisture loss.
-

4. Phenotyping for graft (in)-compatibility three months after grafting.

Graft take, graft length and graft diameter are evaluated three months after grafting. Grafts are cut 1cm above and below the graft union, fixed in ethanol (96%)/acetic acid 3:1 (v/v) over 24 h, then transferred to ethanol (70%) and stored at 4 °C for conservation (Irisarri et al. 2019, Irisarri et al. 2021). Longitudinal free-hand sections are obtained from the surface of the graft in all unions with a high-profile microtome blade (Feather Japan). The longitudinal sections are transferred into Petri dishes and stained for 30s with cellulose-specific dye solution in distilled water 0.07% (w/v). Currently, the sections are being observed using an Olympus BH2-RFCA fluorescence microscope equipped with a digital imaging system through a USB 2 uEye SE camera (IDS, Obersulm, Germany). Three graft unions are tested for every graft combination. Assignment of phenotypic scores to individuals is based on cell pattern, like cell arrangement, cell shape, and cell proliferation at the graft interface. The classification is done from 1, when the union is completely filled with ordered cells, to 5, when the space between scion–rootstock is practically empty (Irisarri et al. 2021).

5. Anatomical observations one year after grafting.

10 leaves of each graft combination are collected to measure their area by scanning and subsequent analysis with the package LeafArea using ImageJ software (NIH, Denvor, CO, USA, <http://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>), to run within R software (ver. 3.5.0; R Core Team, 2017). After growth measurement one year after grafting, the internal characterization of the graft unions is performed through a longitudinal cut at the graft area with a DW876 saw (Dewalt, Perugia, Italy) and anatomy on the surface of the union is observed using a stereomicroscope (Wild Heerbrugg, Heerbrugg, Switzerland) equipped with a digital imaging system through a USB 2uEye SEcamera (IDS, Obersulm, Germany). Each individual combination is classified according to the graft union line, in five categories (A–E). ‘A’ represents a perfect union in which the graft line is almost invisible. ‘B’ has some structural defects with slight discontinuity between the wood and the bark or involution of the cambium in the graft interface. ‘C’ is characterized by an evident layer of parenchymal tissue in the wood and bark or in the union. ‘D’ has discontinuities in practically the entire line between scion and rootstock. Finally, ‘E’ is characterized by broken unions and dead tissue around the graft interface. When most of the unions of a graft combinations are classified in ‘A’ and ‘B’, they can be considered compatible. However, if the majority are in ‘D’ and ‘E’, they are considered incompatible.

References:

- Irisarri, P., Errea, P., Pina, A., 2021. Physiological and molecular characterization of new apricot cultivars grafted on different *Prunus* rootstocks. *Agronomy* 11, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11081464>
- Irisarri, P., Zhebentyayeva T., Errea P., Pina A., 2019. Inheritance of self- and graft-incompatibility traits in an F1 apricot progeny. *PLoS One* 14, e0216371. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0216371

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.4	SOURCES : FEM
	SAMPLE PROCESSING FOR METABOLITE ANALYSES OF FRUIT AND LEAVES IN <i>MALUS</i>	Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 02/12/2024 Date of update : Contact person : Nicola BUSATTO nicola.busatto@fmach.it

Objectives

The purpose of this protocol is to prepare biological or chemical samples for long-term storage or further analysis by removing water content through lyophilization (freeze-drying). Cryogenic grinding ensures the material remains intact and homogeneous, preventing degradation caused by enzymatic activity or heat. The process minimizes contamination, preserves the structural and chemical properties of the sample, and facilitates handling and storage in a stable, dry state. This method is commonly used in molecular biology, biochemistry, and other fields requiring high-quality sample preservation.

Materials required

- Biological material
- Mortar and pestle or cryogenic grinder
- Liquid nitrogen (LN2)
- Freeze dryer (lyophilizer) connected to a vacuum pump.
- Falcon tubes
- Parafilm

Safety equipment:

- Cryogenic gloves
- Safety goggles
- Lab coat

Step by step methodology

5. Collect the samples and slice them in small pieces if working with fruit flesh.
6. Submerge the material in liquid nitrogen until it is frozen solid
7. Grind the material to a fine powder while continuously maintaining freezing temperatures (below -60°C). For leaves, a mortar and pestle are sufficient. In the case of fruit pulp, a cryogenic grinder (e.g., IKA A11 analytical mill) is recommended.
8. Transfer the ground material into a pre-chilled Falcon tube using a pre-chilled spatula. If storing in a -80°C freezer for later analysis, ensure you pierce a hole in the cap to allow residual nitrogen to escape.
9. Aliquot the ground material into new Falcon tubes for the dessication process.
10. Pre-cool the lyophilizer to the desired condenser temperature (typically -50°C to -80°C).
11. Place the flasks into the lyophilizer, covering the openings of the tubes with parafilm pierced with holes to avoid contamination while allowing moisture to evaporate.
12. Initiate the lyophilizer vacuum system as per the manufacturer's instructions.
13. Let the samples dry for 24–48 hours, depending on the volume of the material and the amount of water trapped in it.
14. Allow the system to return to atmospheric pressure by venting it.
15. Remove the samples and immediately seal them with airtight lids or parafilm to prevent moisture absorption.
16. Store the lyophilized material at -80°C.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.4	SOURCES : FEM
	POLYPHENOL QUANTIFICATION IN MALUS TISSUES	Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 02/12/2024 Date of update : Contact person : Nicola BUSATTO nicola.busatto@fmach.it

Objectives

This protocol provides the step-by-step method for extracting and quantifying phenolic compounds in apple tissues using HPLC coupled with mass spectrometry. It is designed to ensure accurate and reproducible results, and it is based on the methods described by Vrhovsek *et al.* (2012), and Busatto *et al.* (2014) for precise extraction and quantification of phenolic compounds.

Step by step methodology

Extraction and filtration

1. First Extraction:

- Extract the powdered tissue with 5 mL of a water/methanol/chloroform solution (20:40:40, v/v/v). 2 grams of fresh material are used, while for lyophilized material 100 mg are sufficient.
- Centrifuge the mixture at **1000g at 4°C for 10 minutes**.
- Retain the aqueous/methanol phase (upper phase).

2. Second Extraction:

- Combine the aqueous/methanol phase with 2.4 mL of a water/methanol solution (1:2, v/v).
- Centrifuge again at **1000g at 4°C for 10 minutes**.
- Combine the upper phases from the two extractions into a single solution, adjusting to a final volume of **10 mL**.
- If the starting material was **lyophilized**, the solution obtained from the previous steps should be **evaporated to dryness** and then resuspended in **500 µL of a water/methanol solution (1:2, v/v)**.

3. Filtration:

- Filter the combined solution using a **0.2 µm PTFE filter**.
- Store the filtrate at -20°C until HPLC analysis.

HPLC Analysis

5. Instrumentation and Solvents:

- Use a **Waters Acquity UPLC system** coupled with a **Waters Xevo TQMS** mass spectrometer in ESI ionization mode.

- Employ a **Waters Acquity HSST3 column (1.8 µm, 100 mm x 2.1 mm)**.
- Solvent A: Water with 0.1% formic acid.
- Solvent B: Acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid.

6. Gradient Profile (Flow rate: 0.4 mL/min):

- The separation flow was 0.4 ml/min with a gradient profile of 0 m, 5% B, from 0 to 3 min, linear gradient to 20% B, from 3 to 4.3 min, isocratic 20% B, from 4.3 to 9 min, linear gradient to 45% B, from 9 to 11 min, linear gradient to 100% B, from 11 to 13 min, wash at 100% B, from 13.1 to 15 min, back to initial condition of 5% B

7. Injection:

- Inject **2 µL** of both the standard solution and the sample.
- Maintain the samples at **6°C** during analysis.

8. Mass Spectrometry Conditions:

- Perform mass spectrometry analysis using a Waters Xevo TQMS with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source. Set the capillary voltage to: 3.5 kV for positive ionization mode, and -2.5 kV for negative ionization mode.
- Analyze each phenolic compound using the optimized MRM (Multiple Reaction Monitoring) conditions as described by Vrhovsek et al.

References

Busatto N, Farneti B, Tadiello A, Vrhovsek U, Cappellin L, Biasioli F, et al. Target metabolite and gene transcription profiling during the development of superficial scald in apple (*Malus x domestica* Borkh). BMC Plant Biol. 2014; 14, 193

Vrhovsek U, Masuero D, Gasperotti M, Franceschi P, Caputi L, Viola R, Mattivi F. A versatile targeted metabolomics method for the rapid quantification of multiple classes of phenolics in fruits and beverages. J. Agric. Food Chem. 2012; 60, 8831–8840.

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.4	SOURCES : INRAE BFP
	METABOLITE EXTRACTION IN WILD APRICOT	Metabolome Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 04/12/2024 Date of update : Contact person : Pierre PETRIACQ pierre.petriacq@inrae.fr

Objectives

The purpose of this protocol is to describe a robotic approach for the automated extraction of metabolites, designed for both targeted and untargeted metabolomics. This high-throughput method ensures reproducible and efficient sample preparation from various biological tissues.

Materials required

- 10 mg of grinded lyophilized biological material
- Ethanol
- Formic Acid
- Methyl vanillate
- Millipore water
- Micronics tubes
- 96-well MultiScreenGV sterile plate 0.22 µm Durapore
- Hamilton STAR 4/96 Iswap ML robot

Safety equipment:

- Safety goggles
- Lab coat
- Gloves

Step by step methodology

1. Extraction using the STAR 4/96 Iswap ML robot
 - a. *This process should be carried out at 4°C*
 - b. Addition of 300 µL of solvent (containing 80 % (v/v) Ethanol and 0.1 % (v/v) Formic Acid with 0.25 mg/mL Methyl Vanillate) to the lyophilized material
 - c. Shake at 500 rpm for 30 seconds
 - d. Sonication 15 min in ice-cold water
 - e. Centrifugation at max speed for 3 minutes
 - f. Collect the supernatant (~ 300 µL) in Micronics tubes
 - g. Repeat once to obtain 600 µL of extract
 - h. Samples can be capped and stored at -20°C before further use
2. Filtration using the STARlet 96 ML robot
 - a. *This process should be carried out at 4°C*
 - b. Deposition of extracts on filters
 - c. Centrifugation (800 g – 1 min)
 - d. Collection of filtered extracts on new Micronics tubes
3. QC preparation using the STARlet 96 ML robot
 - a. *This process should be carried out at 4°C*
 - b. Sampling and mix of 50 µL of each extract
 - c. Vortex
4. Samples can be stored at -20°C before analysis

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.4	SOURCES : INRAE GAFL
	NEAR-INFRARED MEASUREMENTS IN WILD APRICOT	Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 18/10/24 Date of update : Contact person : Morgane ROTH morgane.roth@inrae.fr

Objective

Use of a near-infrared (NIRS) spectrometer to acquire near-infrared spectra from fresh *P. armeniaca* leaves in the orchard.

Material

Spectrometer: QualitySpec® Trek ASD portable (350 à 2500 nm) set to 10 scans per spectrum

Plant material

Fresh leaves recently collected from the tree in the orchard. Within an orchard, the leaves should be collected always at the same height and with the same exposition (same side of the row).

Procedure

1. Spectrometer Setup

Follow the instruction in the QualitySpec® Trek User Manual to properly set up the spectrometer

2. Sample Preparation

Place the adaxial side of the leaf on the spectrometer window avoiding the leaf vein.
Magnetize the Sample Clip on the abaxial face.

3. Acquisition of Spectra

Pull trigger to collect spectral data

Record the acquisition number and its corresponding leaf sample

	PHENOTYPING PROTOCOL T3.5	SOURCES : UNIBAS Version : 1.0 Date of set up: 9/12/24 Date of update : Contact person : Angelo NOLE angelo.nole@unibas.it
	Wood anatomy and quality assessment and Leaf functional traits	

Objective

Use of the wood core samplings to identify ecophysiological traits for different collection of ex-situ CWR species. Main activities have been related to define a suitable protocol to identify morphometrics traits and wood anatomy, contributing to describe collections' functional traits and wood quality to emphasize the use of the species.

Material

1. **Wood anatomy** and quality samples are obtained by means of a 0.5-mm increment borer (Pressler Borer; Haglof, Sweden) which is a simple metal tube that can be driven into a tree to get a core extending from bark to centre. The main issue is related to the dimensions of orchard trees generally characterized by small diameters. Thus sampling activity will be related to wood core extraction on mature trees with minimum 15 cm diameter. This core is split in the laboratory, the rings representing the increment during annual growing seasons are counted and measured based on a dendrochronological approach. The measured width of the ring (i.e., the amount of growth) for each year is determined by various internal and external factors, but it tends to vary mainly in proportion to either the amount of available precipitation or the prevailing temperatures.
2. **Leaf functional traits** are derived from leaf anatomical characteristics describing leaf water transport function, representing a proxy of the efficiency and safety of plant water transport systems. The Petiole XLA (xylem to leaf area ratio) define the ratio between the cross-sectional XA at the petiole divided by the downstream leaf area (XLA_{petiole}).

Plant material

Wood samples extracted with a 0.5 mm Pressler borer collected from the tree in the orchard. Within an orchard, the leaves should be collected always at the same height and with the same exposition (same side of the row).

Fresh leaves with petiole collected from the same orchard trees used for wood core anatomy analysis.

Procedure

1. **Wood anatomy and quality:** wood core extraction using a 0.5 mm Pressler borer for orchard trees with a diameter > 10 cm. Pressler Borer need to be properly used by a trained user in order to avoid damages to the trees and spreading of diseases (pruning mastics and disinfection are mandatory)
2. **Leaf functional traits** : Leaves need to be collected complete with petiole, leaf area need to be measured or scanned using a reference bar for leaf area calculation (for fast field measurements it can be used different smartphone apps as "Petiole", "LeafByte" or "Easy

Leaf Area". Leaves measured need to be sent to UNIBAS Laboratory for measurement of petiole xylem area.

3. For selected trees a structural digital 3D analysis of the crown structure could be performed using Laser Scanner Technology (Leika BLK360)

Pressler Borer

Dendro-anatomical technique

Malus sylvestris petiole quantitative wood anatomy for XLA_{petiole} calculation.

Malus sylvestris 3D digital model (Leika BLK360)